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Concern about the Loss of Biodiversity in the Italian Regions

It increased in the Italian regions by an average of 48.76%.

Istat calculates the value of the concern for the loss of biodiversity. The variable is defined as the percentage of people aged 14 and over who consider the extinction of plant/animal species among their top 5 priority environmental concerns. The data refers to the period between 2012 and 2022 for the 20 Italian regions.

Ranking of Italian regions by value of concern for biodiversity loss in Italian regions in 2022. The updated 2022 data on concern for biodiversity loss in different Italian regions shows the current situation of biological variety in each area. Sardinia has the highest biodiversity among the regions considered, suggesting a particularly rich and diversified environmental situation with a value of 28.6. There are regions that in 2022 showed values above the average, namely Lazio (25.7), Lombardy (25.8), Piedmont (25.4), Tuscany (25.2), Veneto (24.8), Friuli-Venezia Giulia (25.7). There are also some regions that recorded an average value, namely: Valle d'Aosta (24.7), Liguria (24.4), Emilia-Romagna (24.3), Marche (24.2), Trentino- Alto Adige (24.3). Among the regions below the average values are Umbria (23.6), Abruzzo (23.8), Calabria (21.7), Campania (21.5), Sicily (20.7). These regions show lower than average biodiversity values, and may require greater attention to conservation and environmental management strategies. The following regions, however, present a critical value: Puglia (18.3), Basilicata (19.5), Molise (21.9). These regions have particularly low values of concern for biodiversity loss and may face significant challenges in conserving local ecosystems. These data highlight the importance of considering the current biodiversity situation as part of a broader framework for environmental conservation. Targeted strategies and actions are needed to address the specific challenges of each region and to promote sustainable management of natural resources at the national level.

Changes in concern about biodiversity loss in Italian regions between 2012 and 2022. The data suggest a significant improvement in concern about biodiversity loss in many Italian regions during the period considered. The numbers indicate increased concern about biodiversity loss in many regions during this period. Regions such as Abruzzo, Campania, Marche and Sicily have experienced notable increases, indicating a significant commitment to biodiversity conservation. These results may reflect effective environmental policies or specific conservation programs implemented in these regions. Regions such as Lazio, Tuscany, Umbria and Emilia-Romagna have recorded increases that exceed the national average. This can be attributed to sustained efforts towards environmental protection and innovative approaches in natural resource management. Some regions, including Lombardy, Piedmont and Veneto, showed moderate but still significant increases. These results can be the result of sustainability-oriented land management policies. Valle d'Aosta, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Basilicata and Calabria recorded lower than average increases. These trends may require

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greater attention to specific biodiversity challenges in these regions. Trentino-Alto Adige, Molise and Puglia showed a lower variation than the national average. These findings may require deeper analysis to understand the local dynamics influencing biodiversity. Liguria and Sardinia have recorded variations that suggest a stable situation or a slight increase. These trends may require ongoing monitoring to assess any changes over time.

Changes in concern about biodiversity loss in Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. The analysis of data on concern about biodiversity loss in different Italian regions between 2012 and 2022 shows some interesting trends. The regions that experienced the greatest absolute increases were the Centre, followed by the Islands and the South. These regions recorded increases of 8.9, 9.4 and 8.5 respectively. The regions of Southern Italy and the Islands show the highest percentage changes, with increases of 65.89% and 70.68%, respectively. This suggests that these areas have made significant progress in biodiversity sensitivity. The North, North-West and North-East recorded percentage increases between 43.60% and 44.89%, indicating considerable but less marked efforts compared to the Central, Southern and Islands regions. The Center recorded the highest percentage change of 54.60%. This could be attributed to more intensive environmental policies or increased awareness in the region. The Islands, although they have a high percentage change, were already starting from a relatively low level in 2012. On the other hand, the Northwest had the highest level in 2012, but the percentage change is slightly lower than other regions. Overall, Italy shows significant commitment to biodiversity conservation, with all regions showing positive increases. However, the situation varies greatly from one region to another. These data highlight the importance of considering not only absolute variation but also percentage variation, as it provides a more complete picture of the dynamics of sensitivity towards biodiversity. Furthermore, they suggest that the South and Islands may require particular attention and ongoing efforts to maintain and improve biodiversity over time.

Clustering with k-Means algorithms. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Molise, Campania, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Sicily;
- Cluster 2: Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Alto Adige, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Tuscany, Umbria, Marche, Lazio, Abruzzo, Sardinia.

Sensitivity to biodiversity issues tends to be much higher in northern regions than in southern regions. The only two southern regions that have levels of sensitivity to environmental issues such as to participate in the cluster of regions of Central-Northern Italy are Abruzzo and Sardinia. The perception of biodiversity and sensitivity towards environmental issues can be influenced by various socio-economic, cultural and geographical factors. Southern regions may be more focused on immediate economic challenges, such as unemployment or poverty, than environmental issues. The need to address urgent economic problems could lead to less attention to biodiversity. North-central Italy often has a greater concentration of industrial activities and businesses, with greater awareness of environmental issues. The southern regions, characterized by a greater presence of agricultural activities and traditional sectors, show lower environmental sensitivity. North-central regions may have implemented more effective educational programs on biodiversity and the importance of environmental conservation. Greater environmental education can contribute to greater awareness and awareness. Southern communities may be more tied to agricultural traditions or traditional activities that may not promote strong environmental awareness. Changes in lifestyle patterns can impact sensitivity to biodiversity. Cultural and mentality differences can play an important role. Some regions may consider environmental issues less critical than others, influencing perceptions of biodiversity. The environmental history of regions can influence current perceptions. Regions with a history of lower environmental impact may perceive biodiversity as less threatened. However,

biodiversity sensitivity is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon that can change over time in response to multiple factors. Promoting environmental sensitivity requires educational efforts, community involvement and environmental policies that respond to the specificities of each region.

A regression model for estimating Concern for Biodiversity Loss-CBL. Below we present a regression model for estimating concern about biodiversity loss. To this end, I used the following variables for the estimate: Wastewater Treatment-WT, Municipal Waste Products-MWP, Soil Waterproofing by Artificial Cover-SWAC, Transfer of Urban Waste to Landfill-TUWL. The following econometric models were used for the estimation: Panel Data with Fixed Effects, Panel Data with Variable Effects, Pooled Ordinary Least Squares-OLS, Weighted Least Squares-WLS. The following equation was estimated:

$$CBL_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(WT)_{it} + \beta_2(MWP)_{it} + \beta_3(SWAC) + \beta_4(TUWL)_{it}$$

With $i=20$ and $t=[2012;2022]$.

The data shows the presence of a positive relationship between the value of PPB and the value of

- *Wastewater Treatment-WT*: data analysis shows a positive relationship between the value of "Concern for biodiversity loss" and the value of "Wastewater treatment". This implies that, in general, in regions or geographical areas where there is greater concern about biodiversity loss, a greater commitment to wastewater treatment is also observed. One possible interpretation of this relationship could be that communities or regions that are more sensitive and aware of biodiversity issues are also more likely to adopt sustainable policies and practices to manage water resources, such as wastewater treatment. This positive relationship suggests a link between general environmental concern and specific actions aimed at mitigating environmental impacts, in this case focused on wastewater treatment.
- *Municipal Waste Products-MWP*: data analysis suggests a positive relationship between the value of "Concern for biodiversity loss" and the value of "Municipal waste produced". This indicates that, in general, in regions or geographical areas where there is greater concern about biodiversity loss, greater production of municipal waste is also observed. This relationship could be interpreted in several ways. A possible explanation could be that regions with greater environmental awareness and concern for biodiversity may also be more attentive to the environmental impacts of municipal waste production. As a result, they may adopt consumption or waste management practices that reflect their environmental sensitivity.

The data shows the presence of a negative relationship between the value of PPB and the value of

- *Soil Waterproofing by Artificial Cover-SWAC*: data analysis suggests a negative relationship between the value of "Concern for biodiversity loss" and the value of "Soil sealing by artificial cover". This indicates that in regions or geographic areas where there is greater concern about biodiversity loss, less soil sealing due to artificial covers is observed. This relationship could be interpreted in various ways. A possible explanation could be that regions more sensitive to biodiversity could adopt more sustainable urban development policies or practices, reducing the impact of soil sealing. Awareness of biodiversity loss could influence land planning decisions, favoring solutions that conserve the nature of the soil and natural habitat. It should be noted that the observed negative relationship does not necessarily imply a direct cause-and-effect relationship, and other factors could contribute to this correlation.

- *Transfer of Urban Waste to Landfill-TUWL*: the presence of a negative relationship between the value of "Concern for the loss of biodiversity" and the value of "Transfer of municipal waste to landfill" suggests that, in general, in the regions or areas geographical areas with greater concern for the loss of biodiversity, there is a tendency to send less municipal waste to landfill. This correlation can be interpreted in several ways. One possible explanation could be that more biodiversity-conscious regions adopt more sustainable waste management practices, such as recycling, composting or other forms of disposal that reduce reliance on landfills.

It should be noted that both negative and positive relationships do not imply a direct cause-and-effect relationship, and other factors may contribute to this correlation.

Conclusions. The value of concern for the loss of biodiversity increased in the Italian regions by an average of 48.76%. However, there is a significant difference between the southern regions and the northern regions in terms of concern about biodiversity loss. In fact, northern regions tend to have much higher levels of sensitivity to biodiversity than those of southern regions. Although sensitivity to biodiversity has grown significantly in the southern regions between 2012 and 2022. Promoting sensitivity to biodiversity in Italian regions requires an integrated approach involving economic policies, educational initiatives and collaboration between the public and private sectors. First, it is essential to consider tax incentives to encourage sustainable practices. These could include tax breaks for businesses and citizens who adopt eco-sustainable behaviour, promoting responsible land management and the conservation of natural habitats. Another strategic approach could be financial support for companies that embrace eco-sustainable corporate policies. By offering subsidized financing or tax breaks, the adoption of environmentally friendly production processes can be encouraged, thus contributing to the conservation of biodiversity. At the same time, the allocation of specific funds for biodiversity conservation projects is crucial. This can involve non-governmental organizations, research institutes and local communities, creating a network of actors interested in environmental protection. A significant role in promoting awareness towards biodiversity is played by educational programmes. Investing in educational initiatives ranging from schools to community workshops and media awareness campaigns is key to increasing environmental awareness at all ages. At the same time, the development of sustainable tourism can be an economic driver that contributes to the enhancement of local biodiversity. Incentivizing environmentally friendly tourism facilities can create sustainable economic opportunities. Introducing Payments for Ecosystem Services systems can be another effective tool. These systems offer economic incentives to landowners who maintain or restore ecosystems, recognizing the intrinsic value of the services they provide. Furthermore, environmental certifications can guide consumers towards more sustainable choices, rewarding products and services that respect environmental standards. It is also essential to promote collaboration between the public and private sectors, creating synergies between the various stakeholders. Encouraging research and innovation in the environmental sector is also crucial to developing sustainable technologies and solutions. Finally, investing in sustainable urban redevelopment programs can reduce the environmental impact of urban areas, while providing green spaces that support biodiversity. These policies should be adapted to the peculiarities of each region, considering geographical, cultural and economic differences. However, it is very likely that sensitivity towards biodiversity will continue to grow, especially in the southern regions, due to a greater orientation of the population towards issues of environmental sustainability.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

LABEL	VARIABILI	ACRONONIMO	RELAZIONE
A95	Preoccupazione per la perdita di biodiversità	PPB	
A85	Trattamento delle acque reflue	TAR	POSITIVA
A89	Impermeabilizzazione del suolo da copertura artificiale	ISCA	NEGATIVA
A91	Rifiuti urbani prodotti	RUP	POSITIVA
A92	Conferimento dei rifiuti urbani in discarica	CRUD	NEGATIVA

Clusterizzazione con k-Means (k=2)

Model 39: Pooled OLS, using 380 observations
 Included 20 cross-sectional units
 Time-series length = 19
 Dependent variable: A95

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	67.0476	2.27298	29.50	9.36e-100 ***
A85	0.150723	0.0376943	3.999	7.68e-05 ***
A89	-1.05908	0.303177	-3.493	0.0005 ***
A91	0.0312371	0.00432936	7.215	3.01e-012 ***
A92	-0.139238	0.0337645	-4.124	4.59e-05 ***

Mean dependent var	69.76658	S.D. dependent var	18.56587
Sum squared resid	107450.0	S.E. of regression	16.92730
R-squared	0.177499	Adjusted R-squared	0.168725
F(4, 375)	20.23156	P-value(F)	4.20e-15
Log-likelihood	-1611.672	Akaike criterion	3233.345
Schwarz criterion	3253.046	Hannan-Quinn	3241.162
rho	0.202672	Durbin-Watson	0.957007

Model 40: WLS, using 380 observations
 Included 20 cross-sectional units
 Dependent variable: A95
 Weights based on per-unit error variances

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	68.3092	2.23128	30.61	4.91e-104 ***
A85	0.154954	0.0369222	4.197	3.38e-05 ***
A89	-1.01962	0.295334	-3.452	0.0006 ***
A91	0.0295764	0.00421345	7.020	1.05e-011 ***
A92	-0.168907	0.0334340	-5.052	6.84e-07 ***

Statistics based on the weighted data:

Sum squared resid	378.7817	S.E. of regression	1.005030
R-squared	0.192730	Adjusted R-squared	0.184119
F(4, 375)	22.38216	P-value(F)	1.37e-16
Log-likelihood	-538.5865	Akaike criterion	1087.173
Schwarz criterion	1106.874	Hannan-Quinn	1094.990

Statistics based on the original data:

Mean dependent var	69.76658	S.D. dependent var	18.56587
Sum squared resid	107785.2	S.E. of regression	16.95368

Model 37: Fixed-effects, using 380 observations
 Included 20 cross-sectional units
 Time-series length = 19
 Dependent variable: A95

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	70.8698	2.62734	26.97	4.61e-088 ***
A85	0.146790	0.0352813	4.161	3.98e-05 ***
A89	-0.569855	0.301679	-1.889	0.0597 *
A91	0.0252379	0.00416826	6.055	3.57e-09 ***
A92	-0.215215	0.0451569	-4.766	2.74e-06 ***
Mean dependent var	69.76658	S.D. dependent var	18.56587	
Sum squared resid	85830.54	S.E. of regression	15.52730	
LSDV R-squared	0.342990	Within R-squared	0.199966	
LSDV F(23, 356)	8.080370	F-value(F)	2.50e-21	
Log-likelihood	-1568.989	Akaike criterion	3185.978	
Schwarz criterion	3280.542	Hannan-Quinn	3223.501	
rho	0.018319	Durbin-Watson	1.186662	

Joint test on named regressors -
 Test statistic: $F(4, 356) = 22.2453$
 with p-value = $P(F(4, 356) > 22.2453) = 2.07333e-16$

Test for differing group intercepts -
 Null hypothesis: The groups have a common intercept
 Test statistic: $F(19, 356) = 4.71954$
 with p-value = $P(F(19, 356) > 4.71954) = 8.93982e-10$

Model 38: Random-effects (GLS), using 380 observations
 Using Nerlove's transformation
 Included 20 cross-sectional units
 Time-series length = 19
 Dependent variable: A95

	coefficient	std. error	z	p-value
const	69.7711	3.12656	22.32	2.61e-110 ***
A85	0.145961	0.0349217	4.180	2.92e-05 ***
A89	-0.638974	0.295845	-2.160	0.0308 **
A91	0.0263757	0.00411059	6.417	1.39e-010 ***
A92	-0.193145	0.0415432	-4.649	3.33e-06 ***
Mean dependent var	69.76658	S.D. dependent var	18.56587	
Sum squared resid	109362.5	S.E. of regression	17.05455	
Log-likelihood	-1615.025	Akaike criterion	3240.049	
Schwarz criterion	3259.750	Hannan-Quinn	3247.867	
rho	0.018319	Durbin-Watson	1.186662	

'Between' variance = 68.879
 'Within' variance = 225.87
 theta used for quasi-demeaning = 0.61635
 corr(y, yhat)^2 = 0.164887

Joint test on named regressors -
 Asymptotic test statistic: Chi-square(4) = 89.5457
 with p-value = 1.6444e-18

Breusch-Pagan test -
 Null hypothesis: Variance of the unit-specific error = 0
 Asymptotic test statistic: Chi-square(1) = 64.6411
 with p-value = 8.98607e-16

Hausman test -
 Null hypothesis: GLS estimates are consistent
 Asymptotic test statistic: Chi-square(4) = 8.05753
 with p-value = 0.0894934